

"ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PIGEON PEA PRODUCTION: BENEFICIARY VS. NON-BENEFICIARY FARMERS OF UPPER WARDHA DAM "A. M. Deshmukh¹, Dr. S. S. Thakare², Dr. S. N. Ingle³

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Abstract:

In order to improve irrigation systems, which is especially advantageous for agricultural output, dam construction is essential. This study examines "Economic analysis of pigeon pea production : beneficiary vs non- beneficiary farmers of Upper Wardha Dam", specifically focusing on pigeon pea farmers. The research compares the cost and returns of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers in three tehsils: Morshi, Twisa and Dhamangaon Railway. Data were collected from 30 farmers (15 beneficiary and 15 non-beneficiary) during the year 2023-24. The study explores the cost and returns of pigeon pea production, Results show that beneficiary farmers, who have access to dam water for irrigation, exhibit significantly higher crop yields compared to non-beneficiaries. The output-input ratio at cost 'C₃' for beneficiary farmers at overall level was 1.44, while for non-beneficiaries, it was 1.41, indicating higher profitability among the beneficiary farmer.

Keywords: Beneficiary, Non-beneficiary, Productivity, Input-Output ratio, Pigeon pea.

Introduction:

Agriculture plays a vital role in the socio-economic development of India, contributing significantly to rural livelihoods and food security. In this context, irrigation infrastructure serves as a crucial factor in enhancing agricultural productivity and ensuring stability in crop production. The Upper Wardha Dam, located in Amravati district, Maharashtra, is a significant irrigation project aimed at boosting agricultural output in the region. This study focuses on pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*), a vital pulse crop known for its nutritional value and ability to improve soil fertility through nitrogen fixation.

Pigeon pea is extensively grown in rainfed regions of India, but access to reliable irrigation can significantly influence its production economics. Beneficiary farmers, who have access to irrigation facilities provided by the Upper Wardha Dam, may achieve better yields, reduced production risks, and improved profitability compared to non-beneficiary farmers who rely solely on rainfed farming.

This research aims to evaluate the economic viability and performance of pigeon pea cultivation among beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers. By analyzing input costs, yield differences, gross returns, and net income, the study seeks to provide insights into the role of irrigation infrastructure in enhancing the economic outcomes of pigeon pea farming.

Materials and Methods:

The standard cost concepts i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ were used in present analysis.

Cost A₁: All variable cost excluding family labour cost and including depreciation.

- 13) Value of Hired human labour (HL)
- 14) Value of hired and owned bullock labour (BL)
- 15) Value of hired and owned machine labour (ML)
- 16) Value of seeds
- 17) Value of insecticides and pesticides
- 18) Value of manure
- 19) Value of fertilizers
- 20) Irrigation charges
- 21) Depreciation on implements and farm building
- 22) Land revenue, cesses and other taxes
- 23) Interest on working capital
- 24) Miscellaneous expenses

Cost A₂: Cost A₁ + Rent paid for leased-in land

Cost B₁: Cost A₂ + interest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)

Cost B₂: Cost B₁ + rental value of owned land and rent paid for leased in land.

Cost C₁: Cost B₁ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₂: Cost B₂ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₃: Cost C₂ + 10 per cent of Cost C₂ on account of managerial functions performed by farmers.

Gross and net returns**Gross returns**

Gross return of the farmers under the present study was estimated from returns obtained from sale of main produce.

Gross returns = Value of main produce + Value of by produce

Net returns

Net returns were computed at different costs i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by deducting respective costs from the gross returns.

Net income at cost A₁ = Gross return – cost A₁

Net income at cost A₂ = Gross return – cost A₂

Net income at cost B₁ = Gross return – cost B₁

Net income at cost B₂ = Gross return – cost B₂

Net income at cost C₁ = Gross return – cost C₁

Net income at cost C₂ = Gross return – cost C₂

Net income at cost C₃ = Gross return – cost C₃

Input- output ratio

It was calculated at cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by dividing gross income by respective cost.

Results and discussion:

The findings of the present study as well as relevant discussion have been presented under following heads.

Per hectare input utilization of Pigeon pea.

Pigeon pea, an essential legume in India, is valued for its adaptability to semi-arid conditions, high protein content, and importance in crop rotation systems. It is a significant crop grown by the farmers in the study area. As revealed from Table 1 at overall level use of manure of beneficiary farm (0.93 tonnes) was slightly more than non-beneficiary farms (0.6 tonnes). Beneficiary farmers applied more quantity of fertilizers than the non-beneficiary farms. Use of hired human labour days on beneficiary farms (33.18 days) and non-beneficiary farmers (29.26 days). Use of family human male and female labour days on beneficiary farms (22.00 days) and non-beneficiary farmers (18.34 days). Use of seed on beneficiary farms was (13.97 kg/ha) and on non-beneficiary farms was 12.04 kg/ha use of seed slightly more than non-beneficiary farms. Intergroup comparison of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farms also revealed the same trend.

Cost of cultivation of pigeon pea for beneficiary farmers:

The share of each item to the total cost i.e., cost C₃ for pigeon pea cultivation. The cost has determined on the basis of standard cost concept i.e., cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂, cost C₃, the different cost concepts have different utilities in research. Here and attempt has been made to estimate the figures of cost of pigeon pea crop of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers in the study area and presented in table 2.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of pigeon pea grown by the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers is presented in Table 2 that, in case of beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of pigeon pea crop for the sample as an overall level was Rs. 59649.44. The per ha. total cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'C₃' ranges from Rs.

60548.03 in head reach, Rs. 56199.91 in mid reach and Rs. 64778.57 in tail reach respectively. In case of beneficiary the per ha. cost of cultivation at overall level i.e., cost A₁ and cost A₂ was Rs. 30908.97 and Rs. 30908.97 respectively which was 51.82 per cent and 51.82 per cent of total cost i.e., cost C₃. The per ha. cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 30256.07 in head reach which was 49.97 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha cost of cultivation in mid reach i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 30783.75 which was 54.78 per cent of total cost i.e., cost C₃. The per ha. cost of cultivation in tail reach at cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 34881.61 which was 53.85 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' respectively.

The per ha. overall cost of beneficiary farmers cost B₁ and B₂ was Rs. 34694.59 (58.16) and Rs. 48942.60 (82.05) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in head reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 36682.02 (60.58) and Rs. 50151.66 (82.83) per cent. The per ha cost B₁ and B₂ in mid reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 32699.66 (58.18) and Rs. 46956.83 (83.55) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in tail reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 37896.61 (58.50) and Rs. 52921.61 (81.70) per cent. In non-beneficiary group costs were lower as compared to beneficiary farmers as there was low level of input used.

In case of beneficiary farmers head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level share of hired human labour (male + female) to total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' accounted 14.88 per cent, 15.12 per cent, 17.72 per cent and 15.88 per cent respectively. This human labour used in various farm operations like ploughing, harrowing, sowing, hoeing, weeding, harvesting etc. Bullock labour accounted in case of head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level 5.04 per cent, 3.71 per cent, 5.00 per cent and 4.46 per cent respectively. Bullock labour used in the farm operation like ploughing, harrowing, hoeing and transport the farm produce from field to farmhouse. Machines used in farm operation like ploughing, harrowing etc. It included the share in total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' in case of head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level were 3.65 per cent, 5.09 per cent, 4.32 per cent and 4.40 per cent respectively. At overall level the machinery cost was slightly more as compared to non-beneficiary farmers.

Cost of cultivation of pigeon pea for non-beneficiary farmers:

The per hectare cost of cultivation of pigeon pea grown by the non-beneficiary farmers is presented in Table 3, that, in case of non-beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of pigeon pea crop for the sample as an overall level was Rs. 46056.32. The per ha. total cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'C₃' ranges from Rs. 45554.49 in small size group, Rs. 45605.82 in medium size group and Rs. 49027.34 for large size group respectively. The per ha. cost in case of large size group of farmers was higher as input use level was higher.

In case of non-beneficiary, the per ha. cost of cultivation at overall level i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 24407.60 which was 53.00 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha. cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was in small size group Rs. 24076.07 which was 52.85 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha cost of cultivation in medium size group i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 25031.74 which was 54.89 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha. Cost of cultivation in large size group is. cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 25826.61 which was 52.68 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' respectively.

The per ha. overall cost of non-beneficiary farmers cost B₁ and B₂ was Rs. 26867.93 (58.34) and Rs. 37583.49 (81.60) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in small size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 25860.10 (56.77) and Rs. 37002.83 (81.23) per cent. The per ha cost B₁ and B₂ in medium size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 26891.11 (58.96) and Rs. 36943.98 (81.01) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in large size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 29579.28 (68.33) and Rs. 40311.90 (82.22) per cent.

In case of non-beneficiary farmers small, medium, large and at overall level share of hired human labour (male + female) to total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' accounted 13.80 per cent, 18.33 per cent, 13.36 per cent and 15.05 per cent respectively. This human labour used in various farm operations like ploughing, harrowing, sowing, hoeing, weeding, harvesting etc. Bullock labour accounted in case of small, medium,

large and at overall level 7.18 per cent, 7.72 per cent, 4.70 per cent and 5.66 per cent respectively. Bullock labour used in the farm operation like ploughing, harrowing, hoeing and transport the farm produce from field to farmhouse. Machines used in farm operation like ploughing, harrowing etc. It included the share in total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' in case of small, medium, large and at overall level were 3.38 per cent, 1.89 per cent, 3.46 per cent and 3.45 per cent respectively.

Per hectare cost and returns of pigeon pea for beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers:

The per hectare cost and returns from pigeon pea is presented in table 4. It is revealed from the table 4, that at in case of beneficiary overall level average gross return worked out to Rs. 86056.50

The net return obtain at various costs were Rs. 55147.53 at cost A₁, Rs. 55147.53 at cost A₂, Rs. 26200.57 at cost B₁, Rs. 37113.90 at cost B₂, Rs. 46077.74 at cost C₁, Rs. 31829.73 at cost C₂, Rs. 26407.06 at cost C₃. The highest input-output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in mid reach i.e., 1.53 and lowest input-output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in head reach i.e., 1.34. tail reach input-output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.40. At overall level the input-output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.44.

In case of beneficiary farmers at head reach, mid reach, tail reach and overall level per hectare yield of main produce obtained from pigeon pea 10.10 qt., 10.79 qt., 11.50 qt. and 10.80 qt. respectively, it was more as compared to non-beneficiary farmers which has seen in table 4. Yield increases 2-3 qt. more than the non-beneficiary farmers here impact of upper wardha dam is shown by providing irrigation to crop in dry spell.

In case of non-beneficiary farmers at overall level input output ratio at C₃ was 1.41 and for small, medium and large farmers it was 1.48, 1.33 and 1.33 respectively. It's shown that the beneficiary farmers were more profitable than non-beneficiary farmers the impact of gross returns was observed in case of beneficiary farmers due to irrigation from upper wardha dam in their field.

Conclusion:

It can be concluded that in case of beneficiary farmers higher per hectare input was used than non-beneficiary farmers. The beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of pigeon pea for the sample as an overall was Rs. 5380.93 i.e., cost 'C₃'. In case of non-beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation for pigeon pea crop for the sample as an overall was Rs. 5246.87 i.e., cost 'C₃'. There was more per hectare cost of cultivation in case of beneficiary farmers than non-beneficiary farmers. The per hectare cost and returns from pigeon pea in case of beneficiary at overall level average gross return worked out to the net returns obtained from pigeon pea crop by beneficiary farmer are greater than non-beneficiary farmer. Input-output ratio was also greater than non-beneficiary that means the beneficiary farmers was more profitable as compared to non-beneficiary farmers.

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Table No:1 Input utilization pattern of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers of pigeon pea. (Numbers/ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Head Reach	Mid Reach	Tail Reach	Overall	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	2	3		4	5	6	7	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	17.14	16.29	19.00	17.48	12.36	15.94	12.65	13.41
		Female	Days	14.57	14.30	20.00	15.70	12.40	16.56	12.89	13.68
		Total	Days	31.71	30.59	39.00	33.18	29.26	29.26	29.26	29.26
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	3.32	1.82	3.50	2.88	4.93	5.93	2.66	4.44
		Owned	Days	3.32	2.99	3.00	2.73	2.20	0.93	1.41	0.82
		Total	Days	6.64	4.81	6.50	5.61	7.13	6.86	4.07	5.26
3	Machine charges	Hired	Hrs	3.16	4.32	5.00	4.16	2.36	1.62	2.82	2.63
4	seed		Kg.	12.97	13.95	15.00	13.97	12.15	11.87	12.06	12.04
5	Manures		Tonnes	1.65	3.02	1.00	0.93	0.33	0.25	1.20	0.60
6	Fertilizers	N kg/h	Kg.	28.00	19.00	9.00	18.66	14.16	15.50	17.05	15.48
		P kg/h	Kg.	40.00	38.10	18.00	33.36	25.00	30.00	32.00	28.66
		K kg/h	Kg.	42.10	36.20	18.00	32.10	25.00	30.00	35.00	29.66
		Total	Kg.	114.10	93.30	45.00	45.00	64.16	75.50	84.05	73.80
7	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	10.00	10.00	13.00	10.98	9.16	10.31	9.15	9.32
		Female	Days	9.00	6.00	9.00	9.32	10.16	8.75	9.07	9.02
		Total	Days	19.00	16.00	22.00	22.00	19.32	19.06	18.22	18.34

Table No: 2 Cost of cultivation of pigeon pea of beneficiary farmers. (RS./ha)

Particulars			Head Reach		Mid Reach		Tail Reach		Overall	
Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	4867.76	8.84	4593.78	8.99	5434.00	9.23	4971.84	9.17
		Female	3321.96	6.04	3131.70	6.13	5000.00	8.49	3640.52	6.71
		Total	8189.72	14.88	7725.48	15.12	10434.00	17.72	8612.35	15.88
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	2013.48	2.52	1295.86	1.53	2499.98	2.81	1966.44	2.33
		Owned	2013.48	2.52	1846.68	2.18	1950.00	2.19	1800.00	2.13
		Total	4026.96	5.04	3142.54	3.71	4449.98	5.00	3766.43	4.46
3	Machine charges	Hired	2212.00	3.65	2859.84	5.09	2800.00	4.32	2624.09	4.40
4	Seed	Kilograms	2010.35	3.32	2762.10	4.91	3000.00	4.63	2529.13	4.24
5	Manures	Tonnes	2640.00	4.36	2672.70	4.76	1440.00	2.22	1546.66	2.59
6	Fertilizers	N kg/h	224.28	0.37	152.19	0.27	72.09	0.11	149.47	0.25
		P kg/h	1991.00	3.29	1724.03	3.07	814.50	1.26	1509.54	2.53
		K kg/h	842.00	1.39	724.00	1.29	360.00	0.56	642.00	1.08
		Total	3057.28	5.05	2600.22	4.63	1246.59	1.92	2301.01	3.86
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)	500.00	0.83	650.00	1.16	875.00	1.35	674.17	1.13
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)	507.00	0.84	615.00	1.09	1100.00	1.70	724.31	1.21
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)	1830.00	3.02	1860.00	3.31	2450.00	3.78	2047.24	3.43
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)	282.64	0.47	600.00	1.07	900.00	1.39	649.31	1.09
11	Harvesting	(Rs.)	2525.00	4.17	2697.50	4.80	2875.00	4.44	2700.00	4.53
12	Working Capital	(Rs.)	27780.95	45.88	28185.38	50.15	31570.57	48.74	28174.69	47.23
13	Interest on working Capital	(Rs.)	1666.86	2.75	1691.12	3.01	1894.23	2.92	1690.48	2.83
14	Depreciation	(Rs.)	727.58	1.20	815.00	1.45	1304.31	2.01	948.66	1.59

15	Land Revenue	(Rs.)	80.68	0.13	92.25	0.16	112.50	0.17	95.14	0.16
16	COST "A₁"	(Rs.)	30256.07	49.97	30783.75	54.78	34881.61	53.85	30908.97	51.82
17	Rent paid for Leased in land	(Rs.)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	COST "A₂"	(Rs.)	30256.07	49.97	30783.75	54.78	34881.61	53.85	30908.97	51.82
19	Fixed capital	(Rs.)	64259.50	106.13	19159.09	34.09	30150.00	46.54	37856.20	63.46
20	Interest on Fixed Capital @ 10%	(Rs.)	6425.95	10.61	1915.91	3.41	3015.00	4.65	3785.62	6.35
21	COST "B₁"	(Rs.)	36682.02	60.58	32699.66	58.18	37896.61	58.50	34694.59	58.16
22	Rental Value of Land	(Rs.)	13469.65	22.25	14257.17	25.37	15025.00	23.19	14248.01	23.89
23	COST "B₂"	(Rs.)	50151.66	82.83	46956.83	83.55	52921.61	81.70	48942.60	82.05
24	Family Human Labour	Male	2840.00	4.69	2820.00	5.02	3718.00	5.74	3123.04	5.24
		Female	2052.00	3.39	1314.00	2.34	2250.00	3.47	2161.12	3.62
		Total	4892.00	8.08	4134.00	7.36	5968.00	9.21	5284.16	8.86
25	Cost "C₁"	(Rs.)	41574.02	68.66	36833.66	65.54	43864.61	67.71	39978.76	67.02
26	Cost "C₂"	(Rs.)	55043.66	90.91	51090.83	90.91	58889.61	90.91	54226.77	90.91
27	10% Cost "C₂"	(Rs.)	5504.37		5109.08		5888.96		5422.68	
28	Cost "C₃"	(Rs.)	60548.03	100	56199.91	100	64778.57	100	59649.44	100
29	Yield per hectare	(Qtl)	79966.95		84701.50		88949.97		84523.50	
30	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Qtl)	1335.00		1395.00		1875.00		1535.40	
31	Value of total produce	(Rs.)	81301.95		86096.50		90824.97		86058.90	
32	Per quintal cost of Production	(Rs.)	5862.68		5079.23		5469.88		5380.93	

Table No: 3 Cost of cultivation of pigeon pea of non-beneficiary farmers.

(RS./ha)

Particulars			Small		Medium		Large		Overall	
Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	3467.35	8.37	4217.09	10.17	3478.75	7.81	3674.88	8.78
		Female	2246.51	5.42	3384.37	8.16	2475.91	5.56	2626.56	6.27
		Total	5713.86	13.80	7601.45	18.33	5954.66	13.36	6301.44	15.05
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	3430.54	5.19	3951.51	6.63	1933.31	3.03	3070.79	4.83
		Owned	1320.00	2.00	651.00	1.09	1062.79	1.67	529.25	0.83
		Total	4750.54	7.18	4602.51	7.72	2996.10	4.70	3600.05	5.66
3	Machine charges	Hired	1541.65	3.38	862.49	1.89	1696.68	3.46	1590.55	3.45
4	Seed	Kilograms	1615.22	3.55	2099.92	4.60	1768.72	3.61	1795.77	3.90
5	Manures	Tonnes	866.66	1.90	500.00	1.10	3000.00	6.12	1425.25	3.09
6	Fertilizers	N kg/h	184.65	0.41	202.12	0.44	222.33	0.45	201.86	0.44
		P kg/h	1131.25	2.48	1357.50	2.98	1448.00	2.95	1296.87	2.82
		K kg/h	500.00	1.10	600.00	1.32	700.00	1.43	593.20	1.29
		Total	1815.90	3.99	2159.62	4.74	2370.33	4.83	2091.92	4.54
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)	736.11	1.62	750.00	1.64	707.50	1.44	730.28	1.59
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)	509.00	1.12	531.25	1.16	624.31	1.27	522.00	1.13
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)	1395.83	3.06	1281.25	2.81	1680.57	3.43	1460.19	3.17
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)	541.66	1.19	500.00	1.10	682.64	1.39	577.55	1.25
11	Harvesting	(Rs.)	2152.50	4.73	2030.00	4.45	2182.50	4.45	2130.00	4.62
12	Working Capital	(Rs.)	21638.92	47.50	22918.50	50.25	23664.02	48.27	22224.99	48.26
13	Interest on working Capital	(Rs.)	1298.34	2.85	1375.11	3.02	1419.84	2.90	1333.50	2.90
14	Depreciation	(Rs.)	1019.72	2.24	635.00	1.39	635.00	1.30	738.06	1.60

15	Land Revenue	(Rs.)	119.09	0.26	103.13	0.23	107.75	0.22	111.05	0.24
16	COST "A₁"	(Rs.)	24076.07	52.85	25031.74	54.89	25826.61	52.68	24407.60	53.00
17	Rent paid for Leased in land	(Rs.)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	COST "A₂"	(Rs.)	24076.07	52.85	25031.74	54.89	25826.61	52.68	24407.60	53.00
19	Fixed capital	(Rs.)	17840.28	39.16	18593.75	40.77	37526.72	76.54	24603.35	53.42
20	Interest on Fixed Capital @ 10%	(Rs.)	1784.03	3.92	1859.38	4.08	3752.67	7.65	2460.34	5.34
21	COST "B₁"	(Rs.)	25860.10	56.77	26891.11	58.96	29579.28	60.33	26867.93	58.34
22	Rental Value of Land	(Rs.)	11142.74	24.46	10052.87	22.04	10732.62	21.89	10715.56	23.27
23	COST "B₂"	(Rs.)	37002.83	81.23	36943.98	81.01	40311.90	82.22	37583.49	81.60
24	Family Human Labour	Male	2569.65	5.64	2727.61	5.98	2516.25	5.13	2554.05	5.55
		Female	1840.69	4.04	1788.24	3.92	1742.17	3.55	1731.84	3.76
		Total	4410.34	9.68	4515.85	9.90	4258.42	8.69	4285.89	9.31
25	Cost " C₁ "	(Rs.)	30270.44	66.45	31406.96	68.87	33837.69	69.02	31153.82	67.64
26	Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	41413.18	90.91	41459.83	90.91	44570.31	90.91	41869.38	90.91
27	10% Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	4141.32		4145.98		4457.03		4186.94	
28	Cost " C₃ "	(Rs.)	45554.49	100	45605.82	100	49027.34	100	46056.32	100
29	Yield per hectare	(Qtl)	66124.97		59625.00		63770.21		63606.66	
30	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Qtl)	1446.00		1311.00		1272.00		1353.00	
31	Value of total produce	(Rs.)	67570.97		60936.00		65042.21		64959.66	
32	Per quintal cost of Production	(Rs.)	5122.94		5455.03		5470.26		5246.87	

Table No: 4 Per hectare cost and returns from pigeon pea beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Reach (Beneficiary)				Size of holding (non-beneficiary)				
		Head Reach	Mid Reach	Tail Reach	Overall	Small	Medium	Large	Overall	
1	Main Produce (Qtl.)	10.10	10.79	11.50	10.80	8.61	8.12	8.73	8.52	
	Price (Rs.)	7917.52	7850.00	7734.78	7826.25	7680.02	7342.98	7304.72	7465.57	
	Value of Main Produce (Rs.)	79966.95	84701.50	88949.97	84523.50	66124.97	59625.00	63770.21	63606.66	
2	By Produce(Qtl.)	4.45	4.65	6.25	5.11	4.82	3.37	4.24	4.51	
	Price (Rs.)	300	300	300	300	300.00	300.00	300.00	300.00	
	Value of By Produce (Rs.)	1335	1395	1875	1533	1446.00	1011.00	1272.00	1353.00	
3	Value of Total Produce (Rs.)	81301.95	86096.50	90824.97	86056.50	67570.97	60636.00	65042.21	64959.66	
4	Total Cost					Total Cost				
	Cost A ₁	30256.07	30783.75	34881.61	30908.97	24076.07	25031.74	25826.61	24407.60	
	Cost A ₂	30256.07	30783.75	34881.61	30908.97	24076.07	25031.74	25826.61	24407.60	
	Cost B ₁	36682.02	32699.66	37896.61	34694.59	25860.10	26891.11	29579.28	26867.93	
	Cost B ₂	50151.66	46956.83	52921.61	48942.60	37002.83	36943.98	40311.90	37583.49	
	Cost C ₁	41574.02	4134.00	43864.61	39978.76	30270.44	31406.96	33837.69	31153.82	
	Cost C ₂	55043.66	36833.66	58889.61	54226.77	41413.18	41459.83	44570.31	41869.38	
Cost C ₃	60548.03	56199.91	64778.57	59649.44	45554.49	45605.82	49027.34	46056.32		
5	Net Return Over					Net Return Over				
	Cost A ₁	51045.88	55312.75	55943.36	55147.53	43494.90	35604.26	39215.60	40552.06	
	Cost A ₂	51045.88	55312.75	55943.36	55147.53	43494.90	35604.26	39215.60	40552.06	
	Cost B ₁	44619.93	31915.23	26200.57	26200.57	41710.88	31915.23	26200.57	30847.10	
	Cost B ₂	31150.29	39139.67	37903.36	37113.90	30568.14	23692.02	24730.31	27376.17	

	Cost C ₁	39727.93	81962.50	46960.36	46077.74	37300.53	29229.03	31204.51	33805.83	
	Cost C ₂	26258.29	49262.84	31935.36	31829.73	26157.80	19176.16	20471.89	23090.27	
	Cost C ₃	20753.92	29896.59	26046.40	26407.06	22016.48	15030.18	16014.86	18903.34	
	Input- output Ratio					Input- output Ratio				
	Cost A ₁	2.69	2.80	2.60	2.78	2.81	2.42	2.52	2.66	
	Cost A ₂	2.69	2.80	2.60	2.78	2.81	2.42	2.52	2.66	
	Cost B ₁	2.22	2.63	2.40	2.48	2.61	2.25	2.20	2.42	
	Cost B ₂	1.62	1.83	1.72	1.76	1.83	1.64	1.61	1.73	
	Cost C ₁	2.05	1.05	1.93	1.87	1.81	2.07	2.08	1.92	
	Cost C ₂	1.48	2.34	1.54	1.59	1.63	1.46	1.46	1.55	
6	Cost C ₃	1.34	1.53	1.40	1.44	1.48	1.33	1.33	1.41	